

Studies on the Chelates of *ortho*-Carboxy Benzene Azo Dimethyl Aniline with Divalent Metals

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ortho-Carboxy benzene azo dimethyl aniline, $C_6H_4-(COOH)-N=N-C_6H_4-N(CH_3)_2$ (LH) (an indicator with a pH range 4.5-6.5) possesses a chelating behaviour. Its chelates with a number of divalent metal ions, Mg(II), Ca(II), Sr(II), Ba(II), Zn(II), Cd(II), Pb(II), Ni(II), Cu(II) and Co(II), of the type ML_2 , have been isolated and characterised on the basis of their elemental analyses, ir and visible spectra, and magnetic and molar conductance studies. All the chelates are tetrahedral, except NiL_2 and CuL_2 which are square planar. Only CuL_2 and CoL_2 are paramagnetic, the others are diamagnetic. They all are non-electrolytic.

A perusal of literature¹⁻⁷ reveals numerous ligands containing azo group, $N=N$, the nitrogen of which coordinates to the metal ions. The chelation becomes easier when an *ortho* substituent is an acidic group. The present ligand (LH) contains COOH group as an *ortho* substituent and it forms the six-membered metal chelate rings of greater stability. The reagent LH has been selected as the earlier workers kept it confined as an indicator only and failed to mention its still greater applicability as a ligand. The present investigation is concerned with the isolation and characterisation of a large number of its chelates with divalent metal ions. It is important in the sense that it can be used for the determination of transition as well as normal metals. The methods explored for the preparation of ML_2 type of the chelates are cold operated, rapid and quantitative. Due to the sensitivity of the ligand for a large number of divalent metal ions, its selectivity slightly decreases. The pH values of chelation with various cations are close and inconvenience therefore arises in their separation in the mixture.

Experimental

$MgCl_2 \cdot 6H_2O$, $CaCl_2 \cdot 6H_2O$, $SrCl_2 \cdot 6H_2O$, $BaCl_2 \cdot 2H_2O$, $ZnSO_4 \cdot 7H_2O$, $Cd(NO_3)_2$, $Pb(NO_3)_2$, $NiSO_4 \cdot 6H_2O$, $CuSO_4 \cdot 5H_2O$, $CoCl_2 \cdot 6H_2O$ and *o*-carboxy benzene azo dimethyl aniline (LH) used in the present work were B.D.H. products.

C, H, N and M were analysed by standard methods. The ir spectra in KBr phase in the range 4000-200 cm^{-1} were recorded on Perkin Elmer spectrophotometer, model No. 621. The visible spectra in methanol were recorded using Hilger Uvispek spectrophotometer. Magnetic moment was determined on Gouy's balance. Molar conductance in 10^{-3} M acetone solution was determined by the help of Toshniwal conductivity bridge (cell constant=0.2010).

Ligand solution: 0.02 M solution of the ligand was prepared by dissolving 0.538 g *o*-carboxy benzene azo dimethyl aniline in 50 ml 95% ethanol and then diluting to 100 ml with 1 M NaOH. The solution was yellow in colour.

Preparation of the chelates: The ML_2 chelates were prepared by mixing a slight excess of the ligand solution with 50 ml cold aqueous solution (0.01M) of a metal(II) with constant stirring. The precipitate was allowed to settle for 5-10 min, filtered through a sintered glass crucible, washed 4 times with warm distilled water and dried in an air oven at 110-115°.

The pH of formation of the chelates, their colours, analytical data, molar conductance values, magnetic moment and absorption maxima of their visible spectra are given in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

The chelates are insoluble in water but soluble in methanol, acetone, chloroform and carbondisulphide. They are stable under normal conditions but are decomposed by dilute mineral acids. The precipitate of CoL_2 kept unfiltered for 3-4 days gradually turns to a brown mass.

Molar conductance: Very low values for molar conductance (10.2-6.0 $ohm^{-1} mole^{-1} cm^2$) of the chelates (Table 1) evidently suggest their non-electrolytic nature. The metal : ligand ratio in each of them comes to 1 : 2.

Magnetic moment: In case of CuL_2 , μ_{eff} is 1.9 B.M. which is greater than the spin only value (1.80 B.M.) and may be attributed to the orbital contribution or distortion (Jahn Teller effect) of the octahedral structure to square planar one. In case of CoL_2 , μ_{eff} is 4.4 B.M. which is greater than that of three unpaired electron spin only moment (3.90 B.M.) and suggests it to be tetrahedral. High magnetic moment may be due to spin orbit coupling⁸ (i.e. extra orbital angular

Compound	pH of formation of ML ₂	Colours	TABLE I Analysis % ; Found/(Calcd.)				Δ _M mhos cm ² (R. T.)	λ _{max} cm ⁻¹	μ _{eff} B.M.
			M	C	H	N			
LH	-	Yellow	-	66.90 (66.91)	5.15 (5.20)	15.58 (15.61)	-	-	-
MgL ₂	7.5	Yellow	4.27 (4.28)	64.20 (64.28)	4.96 (5.00)	14.94 (15.00)	10.1	-	diam.
CaL ₂	8.0	Yellow	6.93 (6.94)	62.40 (62.50)	4.80 (4.86)	14.52 (14.58)	10.2	-	diam.
SrL ₂	8.0	Yellow	14.00 (14.04)	57.70 (57.72)	4.40 (4.48)	13.40 (13.46)	8.6	-	diam.
BaL ₂	7.5	Yellow	20.34 (20.35)	53.42 (53.48)	4.06 (4.16)	12.42 (12.48)	6.2	-	diam.
ZnL ₂	8.5	Brown	10.80 (10.81)	59.82 (59.90)	4.60 (4.64)	13.88 (13.96)	9.4	-	diam.
CdL ₂	9.5	Yellow	17.31 (17.33)	54.44 (54.56)	4.04 (4.30)	12.88 (12.94)	8.2	-	diam.
PbL ₂	8.5	White	27.85 (27.86)	48.36 (48.44)	3.64 (3.78)	11.20 (11.30)	6.0	-	diam.
NiL ₂	7.5	Greenish yellow	9.80 (9.82)	60.48 (60.53)	6.68 (4.70)	14.10 (14.12)	8.4	22450	diam.
CuL ₂	8.0	Green	10.58 (10.59)	60.00 (60.04)	4.65 (4.67)	14.00 (14.10)	7.6	17860	1.90
CoL ₂	7.5	Blue	9.89 (9.90)	60.00 (60.15)	4.65 (4.70)	14.10 (14.11)	10.1	17000	4.4

momentum generated on mixing of 4T₂ and 4A₂⁻¹ states). Remaining chelates are diamagnetic. The square planar chelates NiL₂ and CuL₂ involve dsp² hybridisation. The tetrahedral chelates are formed by the use of sp³ hybrid orbitals.

Visible spectra : The visible spectrum of NiL₂ shows an intense band at 22450 cm⁻¹ which is assignable to ¹A_{1g} → ³B_{1g} transition and suggests the square planar geometry of NiL₂. Rana *et al*⁹ have suggested the band at 21280 cm⁻¹ for the square planar Ni(II) complex. The band at 17860 cm⁻¹ in the visible spectrum of CuL₂ is probably due to ³B_{1g} → ³E_g transition and it suggested the square planar geometry. Rana *et al*⁹ reported similar band for square planar Cu(II) chelate. This is also supported by the work of Belford *et al*¹⁰ and Agrawal *et al*¹¹. The blue colour of CoL₂ is due to the appearance of a band at 17000 cm⁻¹ (i.e., in the red part of the spectrum), which is assignable to ⁴A₂(F) → ⁴T₁(P) transition and is in further support of tetrahedral geometry. Other bands fall beyond the limit of the instrument.

Infrared spectra : The ligand, LH, can be expected to contain the following two possible donor groups systems :

The system I provides the positions 1 and 5 as the main binding sites for the metal ions. The ir band at 1610 cm⁻¹, assignable to ν(N=N) of the ligand shifts to lower frequencies at 1565-25 cm⁻¹ in the spectra of the chelates, showing coordination through nitrogen atom (position 5) of azo group

(N=N). Sahu *et al*¹² reported ν(N=N) at 1622 cm⁻¹. Agrawal *et al*¹³ have reported a decrease of (N=N) frequency to around 1425 cm⁻¹ in the complexes. Mathur¹⁴ also reported the down ward shift of ν(N=N) to around 1560-40 cm⁻¹.

Chelation thus occurs through the form I and not through the form II. This is further evidenced from the unchanged frequency of ν(C=O) of COOH group. The ν(C=O) at 1680 cm⁻¹ of the ligand¹⁵ remained unaltered even in the spectra of the chelates, showing that carbonyl oxygen (system II) does not coordinate. On the other hand, OH stretching frequencies of symmetric and asymmetric COOH at 2710 and 1605 cm⁻¹ respectively of the ligand disappear in the spectra of the chelates, showing that COOH group is deprotonated and M-O bond is formed. Kudesia *et al*¹⁶ reported the OH stretching frequency of COOH at 3000-2500 cm⁻¹, while Mathur¹⁴ and McAuliff *et al*¹⁷ observed identical deprotonation of ν_s(COOH) and ν_{as}(COOH) on chelation. The fact is further supported by the appearance of sharp and medium bands at 1605-1580 and 1410-1390 cm⁻¹ due to ν_{as}(COO⁻) and ν_s(COO⁻), respectively in the chelates. Ghosh *et al*¹⁸ reported the ν_{as}(COO⁻) and ν_s(COO⁻) at 1585-75 and 1410-08 cm⁻¹, respectively in the spectra of Hg(II) complexes. Furthermore, the ν(C-O) at 1235-10 cm⁻¹ in the spectra of the chelates also support deprotonation¹⁹.

The ν(C-N) at 1495 cm⁻¹ in the ligand also decreases when nitrogen of ν(N=N) donates a lone pair to metal atoms. As the M-N bond is formed ν(C-N) decreases.

The formation of M-O and M-N bonds are further supported by the appearance of ν(M-O) and ν(M-N) at 525-500 and 470-20 cm⁻¹, respectively in the spectra of the chelates. Mishra²⁰ noted ν(Zn-O) and ν(Zn-N) at 450 and 510 cm⁻¹, respectively.

TABLE 2—INFRARED BANDS OF THE LIGAND AND THE CHELATES (cm⁻¹)

LH	MgL ₂	CaL ₂	SrL ₂	BaL ₂	ZnL ₂	CdL ₂	PbL ₂	NiL ₂	CuL ₂	CoL ₂	Assignment
2850 m	2850 m	2850 m	2850 m	2850 m	2850 m	2850 m	2850 m	2850 m	2850 m	2850 m	N(CH ₃) ₂
2710 vs	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	O-H of ν _s (COOH)
1680 m	1680 m	1680 m	1680 m	1680 m	1680 m	1680 m	1680 m	1680 m	1680 m	1680 m	ν _s (C=O)
1610 s	1525 m	1525 m	1530 m	1535 m	1525 m	1535 m	1545 m	1555 m	1565 m	1560 m	ν(N=N)
1590 s	1580 vs	1580 vs	1585 vs	1590 vs	1580 vs	1595 vs	1605 vs	1585 vs	1590 vs	1592 vs	ν _{as} (COOH) or ν _{as} (COO ⁻)
1495 m	1470 m	1470 m	1475 m	1480 w	1475 w	1480 w	1485 w	1490 w	1485 w	1490 w	ν(C-N)
—	1390 m	1395 m	1395 m	1400 m	1405 m	1402 m	1410 m	1405 m	1400 m	1408 m	ν _s (COO ⁻)
—	1210 m	1215 m	1220 m	1225 m	1215 m	1225 m	1235 m	1230 m	1234 m	1230 m	ν _s (C-O)
890 m	890 m	890 m	890 m	890 m	890 m	890 m	890 m	890 m	890 m	890 m	Ring substitution
—	500 m	505 m	515 m	510 m	515 m	525 m	515 m	510 m	505 m	505 m	ν _s (M-O)
—	420 m	425 m	435 m	440 m	450 m	445 m	445 m	490 m	480 m	495 m	ν _s (M-N)

Mohapatra *et al*¹⁹ reported ν(Zn-O) and ν(Zn-N) at still lower frequencies of 420 and 370 cm⁻¹, respectively. The appearances of ν(M-O) and ν(M-N) around 525-500 and 470-20 cm⁻¹ have also been reported^{14,20-22}. For the conformity of ν(M-O) and ν(M-N) in case of the alkaline earth metals no appropriate evidence can be referred because of little information on analogous system in literature.

From the above evidences, it is suggested that the ligand is bidentate monobasic anion and forms the metal chelates by donation through N of N=N group and by loss of one proton of COOH group. The following tentative structure of the chelates can be proposed

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References

1. W. STOSS and G. H. OSBORN, *J. Chem. Soc. Ind.*, 1944, 63, 249.
2. I. M. KORENMAN, *Z. anal. Chem.*, 1932, 90, 115.

3. F. FEIGL, P. KRUMHOLZ and E. RAJANN, *Microchemie*, 1931, 9, 395.
4. L. P. BIFELD and T. M. PATTRICK, *Ind. Eng. Chem. Anal. Ed.*, 1942, 14, 275.
5. SUBHASH-SATISH, "Advanced Inorganic Chemistry", Pragati Prakashan, Meerut, 5th Edn., 1975.
6. C. K. BHASKARE and S. K. DESHMUKH, *Acta Ciencia Indica*, 1976, 2, 1, 34.
7. S. B. GHOLSE, O. P. SHARMA and R. B. KHARAT, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1978, 55, 776.
8. F. A. COTTON and G. WILKINSON, "Advanced Inorganic Chemistry", Wiley Eastern Private Ltd., New Delhi, 2nd Edn., 1967.
9. A. K. RANA and J. R. SHAH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1981, 58, 1100.
10. R. L. BELFORD and W. A. TEANOS, *Mol. Phys.*, 1963, 6, 121.
11. V. K. AGRAWAL, R. P. MAHESH and P. SINGH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1981, 58, 736.
12. B. K. SAHU and B. K. MOHAPATRA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1979, 56, 825.
13. R. G. AGRAWAL and G. K. AGRAWAL, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1978, 55, 681.
14. KESHAW C. MATHUR, *Acta Ciencia Indica*, 1979, 5, 4, 209.
15. C. B. MAHTO, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1980, 57, 485.
16. V. P. KUDESIA and SUBHASH-SATISH, "Spectrum Analysis", Pragati Prakashan, Meerut, 1972, p. 73, 229.
17. C. A. MCAULIFF and W. D. PERRY, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1969, 634.
18. N. N. GHOSH and G. N. MUKHOPADHYAY, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1978, 55, 3, 313.
19. B. B. MOHAPATRA, H. SAHU, B. K. MOHAPATRA and S. GURU, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1978, 55, 209.
20. N. C. MISHRA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1978, 55, 839.
21. V. K. MISHRA, P. C. DWIVEDI and D. R. GUPTA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1978, 55, 412.
22. C. P. GUPTA, D. K. KANUNGO and R. K. MEHTA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1979, 56, 826.